

ALTERNATING CURRENT ELECTROLYSIS. PART IV. ELECTROLYSIS OF SULPHURIC ACID SOLUTIONS WITH COPPER ELECTRODES

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Chemical effects, produced by passing a square-wave type alternating current between copper electrodes in sulphuric acid solution, have been studied. Hydrogen evolution, takes place at both the electrodes but the rate of gas evolution falls rapidly at one of the electrodes at which gas evolution ceases entirely after some time. Copper goes into solution and the electrodes at the end of the experiment are covered with a deposit of copper. The volume of hydrogen evolved diminishes markedly with frequency of alternation and concentration of electrolyte, and increases with current density, temperature and area of electrodes. The rate of gas evolution is proportional to time during initial stages of experiment but falls off with time.

A mechanism depending upon the dissolution of copper during the anodic cycle and deposition of copper and hydrogen evolution during cathodic cycle has been proposed. The fall in the rate of gas evolution is tentatively ascribed to the surface being replaced by electrodeposited copper having entirely different surface characteristics.

The present work is in continuation of the investigation on alternating current electrolysis, using square-wave type A. C. (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 278). Copper electrodes are chosen mainly because copper will function as an attackable electrode in sulphuric acid solutions. The effects of frequency, current density, temperature, concentration of electrolyte and duration of electrolysis have been studied with a view to gaining an insight into the mechanism of electrode reactions in alternating current electrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement was the same as used in the previous investigation (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 69). The electrodes were cut from Kahlbaum extra pure electrolytic copper foil. These were sealed into J-shaped glass tubing, lead glass being used for sealing copper into glass. The electrolyte was prepared from G. R. sulphuric acid and standardised against standard NaOH. The electrode gases were collected in gas collecting cups attached to calibrated gas burettes. The analysis of gas mixtures was done by absorbing the gas in alkaline pyrogallol. The gas mixture, comprising only hydrogen and oxygen, on absorption by pyrogallol afforded the volume of oxygen. The residual gas was found to be only hydrogen. In all the experiments there was complete absence of oxygen in the electrode gas.

The electrodes were cleansed with very dilute nitric acid and then washed with plenty of distilled water. Finally, the electrodes were dipped in dilute ammonia solution, and after washing with water, were immediately used for the experiment. This treatment was found to furnish reproducible results.

It was observed during electrolysis that on switching on current, gas evolution took place on both the electrodes, but in a short time, depending on the frequency,

current density etc., one of the electrodes lost its activity of gas evolution gradually, and ultimately gas evolution stopped entirely at this electrode. Although the other electrode continued to evolve gas, but with time, the rate of gas evolution also, slowed down. At the end of the experiment, a fine non-adhering deposit of copper was observed on both the electrodes. The electrolyte also became faint blue due to the dissolution of copper at the electrodes.

Table I shows the effect of frequency of alternation on the total volume of hydrogen evolved at each electrode. In this and other tables, the term 'Electrode-I' is applied to any one of the electrodes in an experiment. It does not mean that 'Electrode-I' in all experiments is the same piece of copper used.

TABLE I

Area of electrodes = 4 cm². Current = 1 ampere.

Frequency (per sec.).	Electrolyte : N/5-H ₂ SO ₄ . Ampere hours passed = 1.5.		Frequency (per sec.).	Electrolyte : N/20-H ₂ SO ₄ . Ampere hours passed = 1.0.	
	Volume of H ₂ by			Volume of H ₂ by	
	Electrode-I.	Electrode-II.		Electrode-I.	Electrode-II.
5	39.6 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	3	48.4 c.c.	40.0 c.c.
10	15.8	0.2	5	35.6	34.2
20	5.5	0.2	10	23.0	13.5
30	5.3	0.2	20	12.4	4.1
40	4.0	0.2	30	9.3	7.0
			40	8.3	4.7

Table II records the effect of current density on the volume of gas evolved at each electrode. It is to be observed here that the amounts of gas evolved at the two electrodes are not the same, and in different experiments the ratio of volume of gas evolved at electrode-I/volume of gas evolved at electrode-II is not identical. Table III shows the effect of time on the volume of gas evolved at an electrode.

TABLE II

Electrolyte : N/20-H₂SO₄. Frequency = 10 per second. Ampere hours passed = 1
Area of electrodes = 4 cm².

Current density.	Volume of H ₂ .	
	Electrode-I.	Electrode-II.
125.0 ma/sq.cm.	9.6 c.c.	5.0 c.c.
187.5	19.9	14.6
250.0	23.0	20.5
312.5	31.2	26.4
375.0	35.0	29.3
437.5	40.0	33.8

TABLE III

Electrolyte: $N/20\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Area of electrodes = 4 sq. cm. Current = 1 amp.

Frequency = 10 per second.				Frequency = 20 per second.			
Time.	Vol. of H_2 .	Time.	Vol. of H_2 .	Time.	Vol. of H_2 .	Time.	Vol. of H_2 .
2 min.	0.8 c.c.	30 min.	7.7 c.c.	5 min.	1.3 c.c.	37 min.	7.8 c.c.
5	1.7	35	9.2	10	2.2	44	9.3
10	2.6	40	10.5	15	3.2	50	10.4
15	4.2	45	11.9	20	4.2	60	12.6
20	5.4	50	13.5	25	5.3		
25	6.4	60	16.3	30	6.4		

Table IV shows the influence of concentration of electrolyte on the volume of gas evolved at each electrode and Table V, the effect of temperature on the volume of hydrogen evolved at each electrode.

TABLE IV

Area of electrodes = 4 cm². Current = 1 amp. Duration of electrolysis = 1 hr.

Conc. of H_2SO_4	...	$N/2$	$N/4$	$N/8$	$N/10$	$N/16$	$N/20$	$N/40$
Vol. of H_2 in c.c.	{ Electrode-I	1.4	5.0	6.2	13.5	16.4	19.8	24.6
	{ Electrode-II	4.6	6.0	11.0	23.0	25.3	27.2	30.3

TABLE V

Electrolyte: $N/20\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Frequency = 10 per sec. Current = 1 amp.
Duration of electrolysis = 60 mins.

Temp.	...	35°	40°	51°	70°	80°
Vol of H_2 in c.c.	{ Electrode-I	23.0	21.0	24.6	30.8	35.8
	{ Electrode-II	13.5	18.5	24.0	29.5	34.0

Table VI shows the influence of area of electrode at the same current density on the volume of gas evolved at each electrode.

TABLE VI

Current density = 500 ma./cm². Amp. hour passed = 1. Frequency = 10 per sec.
Conc. of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = N/20$.

Electrode area (cm ²)	...	2.0	3.2	4.0	5.2	6.0
Vol. of H_2 in c.c.	{ Electrode-I	30.3	23.7	13.5	15.0	17.6
	{ Electrode-II	34.0	30.9	23.0	23.5	20.5

DISCUSSION

The most interesting feature of the present investigation is the totally unsymmetrical behaviour of the electrodes in that one of them continues to function as hydrogen evolving while the other, after showing hydrogen evolving activity for some time, ceases to function as a gas-evolving electrode during the experiment. It has also been observed that if the current is slowly increased, one of the electrodes alone functions as hydrogen-evolving while at the other electrode, the rate of gas evolution decreases rapidly with time. On the other hand, if the current is switched on suddenly, a brief period of gas evolution is observed at the electrode. The gas-evolving electrode, too, gradually loses its gas-evolving activity with time. This phenomenon is more marked in concentrated solutions of sulphuric acid. In very dilute solutions, however, both the electrodes continue to function as hydrogen evolving though the efficiency at the electrodes is never the same.

Another important observation that has been made is that both the electrodes become coated with a non-adherent layer of electrodeposited copper. From the data presented above, it will be seen that the current efficiency of hydrogen evolution falls very rapidly with frequency of alternation, while at the same frequency, the plot of current density against the volume of hydrogen evolved (Table II) is a straight line at higher values of current density. The volume of hydrogen evolved at an electrode is roughly proportional to the time during the initial stages of electrolysis. Lower concentrations of sulphuric acid and higher temperatures favour the evolution of hydrogen. At the same current density, the volume of hydrogen evolved depends on the area of electrodes (Table VI).

When a copper electrode, suspended in a solution of sulphuric acid, is subjected to cathodic and anodic polarisation alternately, the reactions that can take place at the electrode are:

while during the anodic cycle, at lower potentials the metal may go into solution. At higher values of current density, in D. C. electrolysis, copper is known to become passives and evolves oxygen. The latter stage does not seem to occur since oxygen is not found in the electrode gas. Thus, the anodic reactions may be:

Copper will therefore dissolve out during the anodic cycle at some favourable spots on the electrode surface, resulting in the formation of copper sulphate at the metal-solution interface, while some of the copper sulphate may diffuse into the bulk of the solution. The amount of copper sulphate in solution being small, it suggests that the anodic dissolution process is reversed to an appreciable extent during the cathodic cycle:

or

Thus, electrodeposited copper appears on the electrode during the cathodic cycle. As $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ concentration in the vicinity of the electrode is depleted, the electrode potential rises and the discharge of $[\text{H}^+]$ takes place. Thus, near the end of the cathodic cycle, the electrode becomes a hydrogen-evolving one. At higher values of frequency of alternation, the period of duration of a half cycle is small. During the anodic half cycle, most of the copper dissolved at the electrode remains in the vicinity of the electrode. When this electrode is subjected to cathodic polarisation, most of the dissolved copper is deposited on the electrode as the duration of half cycle being small, very little $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ will diffuse into the bulk of the solution. Thus, at higher values of frequency, the chemical effects of one impulse are more or less completely reversed during the next half cycle. Hence, the volume of hydrogen evolved diminishes with frequency. Again, at higher current density, we must expect a greater dissolution resulting in a faster rate of diffusion of $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ into the bulk of solution. Thus, during the cathodic cycle, the depletion in $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ concentration will be brought about much quicker, resulting in a greater evolution of hydrogen. The effect of temperature can be explained by the same mechanism, as higher temperature will increase the rate of diffusion of $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ favouring hydrogen evolution.

With the progress of electrolysis, $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ concentration in the electrolyte will go on increasing as, excepting at higher frequencies, the dissolution and deposition processes are not exactly balanced. This will cause the cathodic behaviour of copper to change altogether as the rate of diffusion of $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ towards the electrode and the rate of deposition may be comparable; hence, the cathodic process may entirely be the deposition of copper, resulting in the stoppage of H_2 -evolution at the electrodes. Why this condition should be obtained at one of the electrodes much earlier than at the other is a point which needs explanation. This behaviour may be due to (i) the covering up of the active centres where either the discharge of $[\text{H}^+]$ or combination of H atoms can occur by electrodeposited copper; (ii) the different history of the electrode in that during electrolysis, the first impulse must be opposite in polarity to that at the other electrode. This may possibly determine the behaviour of the electrode during the rest of the experiment. This point has been verified experimentally as follows. Two copper electrodes were subjected to D. C. electrolysis for a short time in $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. When electrolysis was in progress, A. C. was switched on and the D. C. was stopped by a mechanical device. It was found that the electrode, which was cathodically polarised in D. C. electrolysis, continued to function as gas-evolving in A. C. electrolysis, while the electrode which was subjected to D.C./anodic polarisation did not show any gas evolution in A. C. electrolysis. It seems therefore that the first impulse during A. C. electrolysis is the determining factor in the behaviour of an electrode.

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